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Editor-in-Chief

DR. VIPIN K. SINGH

Editors

DR. PRIYANKA SINGH

DR. BASANTA K. MOHANTA

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Entrepreneurial Opportunities for Tribal Women in Tourism Sector: A Study on Scheduled Areas of Madhya Pradesh

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Abstract

The explicit development of marginalized communities is very important for a developing country. In order to catalyze their growth, self-employment is the best option. But, it is not possible to start business without a systematic investigation. So this study is conducted to investigate the suitable entrepreneurial opportunities in tourism sector, for tribal women residing in the state of Madhya Pradesh. To realize the objectives of present study un-structured interviews and participate observation method is adopted. Implementable suggestions and recommendations are conceived out of this research study.

Key words: Tribal Women, Entrepreneurship, Training, Handicrafts, Scheduled areas.

Introduction

“You can tell the condition of a nation by looking at the status of its women”
—Jawaharlal Nehru

An attempt to write a research paper on the scope of creating entrepreneurial opportunities for tribal women is one of the

most important social concerns. Progress of marginalized communities is treated as important growth indicator and necessary for a developing country like India. Providing employment opportunities to all populace of this country, whether it is Government, non-government or private, is not possible. Hence, helping them to take up entrepreneurial activity is best possible alternative available with the Government. Tribal communities are democratic and house hold responsibility is shared equally between female and male members, so it gives fruitful results if the tribal women are bestowed with the earning opportunities.

Gender based inequalities are scientifically researched by a social watch. It is involved in the collection of data and analysis is done by adopting, systematic methodology for preparation of gender equity index. It is used to categorize different countries. Third world countries are not significantly contributed to the fundamental knowledge of entrepreneurship theories, when compared with developed nations. If any such study is conducted it is confined to specific sectors or groups only. Action and applied research has to be carried out by the educational institutes, social organizations and international agencies to help the tribal women to make successful career in self-employment. The results conceived out of such serious research studies should be transformed into theories and those can be used for guiding women entrepreneurs in general and tribal women in specific. Jyoti Y. depicted Indian women as homely, soft, non-aggressive, introvert and faced cruel behaviour from the day one of her birth or even the days before. They are also facing violence against them, gender inequality, comparative low treatments in the sectors like education, employment, earnings, etc. despite all these problems in the society and within the family, they are involved in nation building.

Modern woman is not equal to men, but they are more and they are confident, intelligent, innovative, talented, educated and creative. The above paragraph stands valid only for few segments or class of women. An attempt is made in this research paper to understand the status of tribal women inhabited in the scheduled areas of Madhya Pradesh. In the above statement status is concerned with their empowerment. Women entrepreneurship also contributes substantially for the economic growth, but unfortunately, some people with traditional mind set are not supporting them. (Kumbhar, V. M. 2).

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this research paper is to investigate the micro-level opportunities in tourism sector, mainly the activities suitable for tribal women, living in scheduled areas of Madhya Pradesh. The measurable and attainable objectives of the study are to know the challenges faced by tribal women in setting up an enterprise. the present paper attempts to mark the Identification of Tourist destination in the scheduled areas of Madhya Pradesh.

Review of Literature

Knowledge is created through the continuous effort made by different individuals in the dynamic environment. According to Sinha, (76) women enter into entrepreneur activity by three type of reasons, these are chance, force and created. Women has the ability to learn fast and cope up with the environment easily if the training is provided to them in a special environment, where only women participants are there. The tailor made training programmes yield better results and they imbibe the skills like confidence, credibility and inter-

personal skills comfortably (Vinnicombe and Singh 294-396). The female Entrepreneurs have to work hard relatively, when compared to the male member to convince the customer, suppliers and run the business successfully. (Shabbir 1). Physical age of the women also play a vital role in diversifying her business, besides this, she has to take care of her home, children, family, relatives and business. If women receives good and supportive family members, her performance is certainly better and she can play all the roles equally good. It is remarkable that the technology helps tribal women to display their goods for potential customers in the physical and virtual markets. Research on various areas of women entrepreneurship is essential in the contemporary, dynamic markets. (De Bruin, A., et al. 223-339). Women always do their work systematically, with lot of patience and commitment. Their contribution also counts, so support from the family members, society and peer groups take them to new heights in their business ventures. The survey of literature on empirical studies in the area of women entrepreneurship revealed that tribal women are still lagging in the areas of education, health, agriculture, political leadership, basic amenities, business, employment, social mobilization. They should be exposed to sensitization on various, schemes, methodologies, and scope for the development. Shivaraj, B. M. C. G. H., and Dileepkumar, M. G. M. (2012). It is essential to know the factors responsible for boosting and motivating women to start business of their own, those factors are leading behaviour, strong determination and risk taking attitude. Panda, S. S. (2013). In order to create successful ventures women should have good education, professional qualifications, managerial skills, passion, radiant personality, independent, decision making ability, proactive and confident. Kaur, G., and Singh, D. S. (2013).

Methodology

The method adopted to realize the objectives of the study are a series of in-depth interviews with local tribal community members, tourism officials and the same assumptions are adopted to other locations, because the target group is more or less same at the all the locations, as understood that they are women members of the tribal groups residing in the same state. Personal semi-structured interviews were conducted with a sample of 25 women members in Anuppur District. Participatory direct observation method is followed to know the daily routine of the women members, their role in earning financial resources to take-care of their family. Further this also provides scope to collect the present tourism related activities available at the destination. Secondary data is collected through the research articles, proceedings of the tribal welfare department, research projects, white papers, unpublished thesis and the authentic documents provided by the entrepreneurship development organizations.

Study Area

Madhya Pradesh is located in the central part of the country, it is otherwise called “Heart of India”. The state is bestowed with rich cultural and heritage resources, monuments, forests, mountain ranges, hill stations, wild life sanctuaries and spiritual destinations. In 1950, former British Central Province, Berar, princely state of Makarai and Chhattisgarh was formed into 3 new states, they are Bhopal, Vindhya Pradesh and Chhattisgarh. Due to the reorganization of states, these three regions merged into Madhya Pradesh, in 1956. It was originally the biggest state in India with 61 districts until 1st November, 2000 and thus divided into Madhya Pradesh and Chhattisgarh after that. Now it is the second largest state in India and the physical areas of this state

occupies 9.38% of the whole country. The main occupation of the people of this state are agriculture, pastoral activity and collection of non timber forest products. Bhopal, Indore, Jabalpur and Gwalior are some of the most advanced cities in terms of industrial development. The scheduled areas of Madhya Pradesh are Alirajpur, Anuppur, Balaghat, Barwani, Betul, Chhindwara, Dhar, Dindori, Hoshangabad, Jabalpur, Jhabua, Khandwa, Khargone, Mandla, Ratlam, Seoni, Shahdol, Sheopur, Sidhi, Singrouli and Umaria.

Position of Tribes

As per the 2011 census, tribes constitute nearly 8.6% of Indian population, mainly they are more populated in north-east and central part of India. The population of Madhya Pradesh is 7,26,26,809., out of this 1,53,16,784 are tribes., from this, 77,19,404, are male and 75,97,380 are female. Total population of Madhya Pradesh comprises 21.1% of scheduled tribes. Six districts in state are having more than 50% and 13 districts are having more than 25 % of tribal population. 31.3% of tribes lives in non-tribal area and 68.7% of tribes lives in scheduled areas. Sex ratio of the tribal population in the state is 983: 1000. Literacy rate among the tribes of the state is 50.6 %. Madhya Pradesh occupies third position in terms of school drop-out of tribal children in India. The state stands first position in the country in terms of pass percentage of tribal students, who appeared for 10th class examination. Government of India, (2013).

They are also facing problems of safe drinking water, housing, electricity, communication, health and there is a serious problems of health workers and doctors in the scheduled areas. The problem is more acute in terms of specialist doctors. Government of India, (2013).

Status of Tribal Women

Tribal communities are democratic in nature, women in tribal communities generally enjoy a superior social status than Indian women in general. Tribal women face a lot of problems like malnutrition, poor health, lack of education, osteoporosis, etc. Hunting, fishing, gathering of forest products, shifting cultivation to settle agriculture, rural crafts and handicrafts are the prime occupations of the tribal communities. A negligible fraction of tribal communities are mendicants, pastoralists and involved in collection of *bedi* leaves, which resembles a situation between nomadic to semi-nomadic lives. Besides routine household work, the tribal women work in the agricultural fields and forests for long hours. Their schedule of long working hours continues even during pregnancy, natal and postnatal stages. They have a negative energy balance, high morbidity rate, and low child survival rate. They suffer from bans, delusions, deprived of the benefits from existing progress, and welfare programmes. Tribal communities have their habitations near by the forests areas, which are rich in minerals. Practical problems faced by these communities are migrations and re-settlements due to different projects like hydro-electric, mining and some special industries, which should be established in those areas only. Loose ends in the government machinery are leading to exploitation of the natural and mineral resources. This uncomfortable social situation leads to the supplanting of their livelihood and even they are not in a position to enjoy their basic rights. Dams, hydroelectric-power, heavy industries, mining, mineral industries are contributing to Indian economy, they are also creating wealth, foreign exchange, direct and indirect employment opportunities, out of all these tribal communities are hardly benefited. As a result they have to undergo stressful conditions like

cultural and social deprivation, land alienation, environmental problems, dislocation and even some times the agencies involved in providing rehabilitation does not do proper Justice to them. During all these problems women has to take more stress, than men. Tribal society in India is unique with diversified nature of people. Venugopal, R. K., & Konchada, S. (2014).

Requirements to Start Enterprise

Tribal women works in unorganized sectors of the rural agriculture, collecting non timber forest produce, etc., for maintenance of their family, if the government provides, some self-employment opportunities, it helps them to lead comfortable livelihood. In order to make them more successful entrepreneurs two thing are very important, they are sensitization towards different schemes provided by the Government and another one is to provide opportunities in work environment. (Dasgupta, T., et al., (2006). Various Government and non-government institutions provide ample training opportunities for progression of tribal communities, but the social and cultural obliges may not permit them to participate, this hold good both in urban and rural areas. The concept of mobile training programmes attracts more number of women participants, because it is comfortable for them and their family members. Another best suitable concept is part-time training programmes, mainly during afternoon or un-season, where they are having leisure time. Stipend, matching grant, subsidy and loan facility help the tribal women to participate in training programmes, and start new business ventures.

Societal approaches decide that specific crafts or small industries are suitable for women, i.e. basket making, weaving, sewing, knitting, teaching, weaving, etc. It is not

possible for them to mend the electrical and mechanical devices. It is very necessary to teach them the basic things about the repair and maintaining. Tribal women are not having basic qualification to make them specialists, but the basic thing can be taught and they can easily learn. (Dasgupta, T., et al., (2006)..

Finance play a very decisive role in launching any prospective venture. The government or responsible institutes should see that the financial resources should be available for the tribal women at right time and accurate amount. Tribal women are not in a situation to invest capital for starting a venture. The financial source for starting a venture is to take bank loan, but there is a cumbersome procedures and they have to mortgage property to obtain loan. It is not possible in case of tribal women, because, whatever the physical assets are there, they are registered on the name of the male members. Hence, it is necessary to arrange working capital comfortably and at their convenience.

Procurement of raw material is one of the most important challenges before the women and next one is to market the finished goods. Tribal women generally approaches middleman to market their goods, but they exploit these innocent women in the best possible ways. The best way to help them is to create suitable marketing place like, hats, exhibitions, etc.

Entrepreneurial Opportunities in Tourism Sector

The present research study reveals that the tribal women are very active and sharing equal or often more responsibility than men for their living. It is understood that their role is significant in family household income, it is better to shape them in a more professional manner, by changing the current

thinking at school level to promote the involvement of women in economic activities. This would be possible by changing the conventional image of women in society and encouragement should be extended by family members. Transport facilities like state road transport services are crucial to facilitate the women to take their products to nearby cities or towns for more competitive price for handcrafts produced by them.

Tribal communities are culturally rich, their authentic dance forms can be exhibited to the tourists. Who are visiting to tourist areas like, Bhandavgadh, Khana, PENCH, National Parks, pilgrimage destinations like Amarkantak, Mahiyar, and Leisure Tourism destinations like Panchmari. The media has a very important role to popularize their services at national and international level. Traditional food stalls are also in good demand.

Guide training should be imparted to tribal women and license should be issued to them. Persons with professional training and license are only allowed to serve as guide. A suitable place with facilities should be earmarked by the authorities and those outlets should be allotted to tribal women only.

Tribal women are allowed to form a group and they should be permitted to maintain tented accommodation facilities in side the reserved forests and wild life sanctuaries.

Tribal women may take up dairy or poultry in a small scale and the products produced by them may be supplied to the hotels and restaurants.

Every tourist destination is bestowed with some souvenirs, tribal women can maintain souvenir shops comfortably without dislocating themselves.

Suggestions and Recommendations

Marketing gaps should be identified by doing specific market survey, this helps them to build good business networks. These women entrepreneurs could be classify into different groups and tailor made facilities like mentoring, guiding and other necessary amenities should be provided. Training in the areas of technology, marketing, finance and project management is essential to shape themselves into successful business communities. NGO's and government bodies should disseminate the information, guidelines, policies related to women entrepreneurship.

Women should try to upgrade themselves in the changing environment by adapting the latest technological advancements. They should acquire the skills and knowledge in all the functional areas of business management, it can facilitate women to excel in decision making process and develop a good business network. Goyal, M., & Parkash, J. (2011).

Women entrepreneurs face the same set of challenges, when compared with their male counterparts. However, female entrepreneurs, need to deal with additional gender related issues. The above factors prevent them to enter into the marketplace, so they should be facilitated to make their entry comfortable. Goyal, M., & Parkash, J. (2011).

Successful women entrepreneurs has to extend their co-operation, guidance, assistance to the new women entering into business or the women who are facing hurdles. Okafor, C., and Amalu, R. (2010). Tribal women should be motivated to move out of their traditional framework, it provides them with more courage and stamina to accept more rewarding and challenging assignments. Advanced training should be provided to tribal women with technical and managerial

skills, so that, they can design innovative products. Sarma, G. (2014). The social and cultural barriers like taboos, superstitions, customs, gender, caste, occupation, and class are not allowing them to gain financial freedom. In order to overcome all these problems, they should be provided with basic education and required skills, (Sindhi, M. S. 2012). A major shift in traditional attitude and mind set of the people in the society can only eliminate the obstacles for tribal women and help them to establish successful enterprises. Mahajan, S. (2013). Whether men or women, their work always helps for the nation building, it also helps their family, in present era of competition women are also willing to take up business activities, and they should be trained in strategic management and risk management. Jyothi, P. N. (2014). India has already experienced the contribution of women entrepreneurs for the growth of economy, women from rural and tribal communities should be trained to utilize the edge of technology, import and export procedures, (Venugopal, R. K., & Konchada, S. 2014). Training and skill development programmes for tribal women make them to eligible for setting up of their own business ventures. Education, liberal thinking, make them radiant and economically independent, (Pushpanadham, K., & Sindhi, S. 2014).

Tribal women should use the schemes and incentives provided by the government to raise the funds, non-governmental organizations should help them in dissemination of government policies and various bodies from time to time, which are related to entrepreneurship.

Conclusion

There is a need for substantial research in the field of entrepreneurship opportunities for tribal women. They are playing vital role in contributing financial resources to

maintain their family. Whether tribal women or men, they are facing lot of challenges in their routine life. Tribal women are facing health problems, lack of education, sanitation, safe drinking water and societal problems. Sometimes the taboos, superstitions also make them tricky. As they are facing difficult situation to lead their livelihood, it is the responsibility of every person, Government and Non-governmental organizations to work for the progression of the tribal communities. In order to empower the tribal women training should be imparted in the fields of finance, management, strategy, book keeping, maintenance of accounts, using technology for optimum results, marketing and production. At the same time financial support should be provided to the tribal women for the establishment of enterprises. Majority of the tribal population resides in scheduled areas of the state. These areas are also having good tourist destinations, which are having ample opportunities to start tribal dance for tourist consumption. Handicraft production and marketing, traditional food stalls, communication stalls, selling drinks and souvenir shops are some of the suitable and convenient opportunities for tribal women residing in scheduled areas of Madhya Pradesh.

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